

Physicochemical Studies of Complexes of Transition Metal Ions with *N*-Hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine

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The solid complexes of Ti^{IV} , V^V , Cr^{VI} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mo^{VI} and U^{VI} with *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (HDPB) have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic, thermal, reflectance and infrared spectral data.

N-Hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (HDPB) and its derivatives have been recently explored as a potential bidentate analytical reagent for the determination of various *d*-group elements. They have been found to be valuable organic analytical reagents for the gravimetric^{1,2}, spectrophotometric³ and solvent extraction³⁻⁵ studies of various metal ions. HDPB has been used in this laboratory for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} . We report here the preparation and characterisation of solid complexes of Ti^{IV} , V^V , Cr^{VI} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mo^{VI} and U^{VI} with HDPB.

Results and Discussion

Analytical and physical data of the complexes are reported in Table 1. Molar conductance values of the complexes in nitrobenzene were found to be in the range $2-15 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ which is close to those reported for non-electrolytes⁷.

Infrared spectra : Various bands observed in the spectra of HDPB and its complexes have been assigned with reference to literature data⁸. HDPB exhibits a sharp band around $3100 cm^{-1}$ which is known to be lowered due to intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonding⁹. However, this band is absent in the spectra of the complexes indicating that proton of the OH groups is replaced by the metal ion upon chelation. The C=N band ($1590 cm^{-1}$) is not influenced by the intramolecular O-H...N bond. In hydroxyamidines this absorption band

appears in the same region despite the presence of strong intramolecular H-bond, the strength of which has been shown to be greater than O-H...O bond. On complex formation, the C-N ligand band ($1425 cm^{-1}$) is displaced to higher frequency ($1430-1440 cm^{-1}$). The N-O ligand band ($930 cm^{-1}$) gets shifted to higher frequency side in the complexes ($940-985 cm^{-1}$) with increase in intensity.

The ligand produces metal complex probably by forming a M-O bond (through the hydroxyl oxygen) and coordination takes place through the formation of a M-N=C type of bond. The formation of M-O-N is also evident from the displacement of N-O stretching frequency of the ligand ($930 cm^{-1}$) to $960 \pm 20 cm^{-1}$ in the complexes¹⁰. All the metal complexes show metal-oxygen stretching vibration between 530 to $555 cm^{-1}$. A new band appears at $440-465 cm^{-1}$ (M-N) in all the complexes. Sharp bands at 1040 , 1015 and $950 cm^{-1}$ are observed in the Ti^{IV} , V^V and Cr^{VI} complexes respectively. In CrO_2 , Cr=O band was reported¹¹ at $935 cm^{-1}$.

The presence of dioxomolybdenum species $O=Mo=O$, in the chelates is established from the infrared spectra of the complexes. The absorption band around $880 cm^{-1}$ arises most likely from MoO_2 asymmetric stretching and that around $915 cm^{-1}$ represents symmetric MoO_2 stretching vibration. The existence of a true dioxomolybdenum species ($O=Mo=O$) is indicated by the lower value of the symmetric stretching frequency, as oxometal cation involving a single oxygen metal multiple covalent

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour, decomp temp °C)	Analysis% Found (Calcd)			μ_{eff} Metal	B M
	C	H	N		
[TiO(HDPB) ₂ H ₂ O]H ₂ O (Yellow, 245)	66.92 (67.66)	4.89 5.04	7.86 8.31	7.50 7.11	Dia
[VO(OH)(HDPB) ₂]2H ₂ O (Dark green, 220)	64.99 (65.71)	4.95 5.19	7.76 8.07	7.64 7.34	Dia
[CrO ₂ (HDPB) ₂]H ₂ O (Brown-red, 245)	67.75 (67.45)	4.66 4.73	7.84 8.28	7.51 7.69	Dia
[Mn(HDPB) ₂ 2H ₂ O] (Brown, 233)	67.98 (68.58)	4.91 5.11	7.99 8.42	8.60 8.26	5.80
[Fe ^{II} (HDPB) ₂ 2H ₂ O] (Purple, 221)	69.02 (68.48)	4.96 5.11	8.59 8.41	8.58 8.39	5.10
[Fe ^{III} (HDPB) ₃]2H ₂ O (Red, 215)	71.50 (71.78)	4.97 5.14	9.10 8.81	6.01 5.86	5.75
[Co(HDPB) ₂ 2H ₂ O] (Yellow, 235)	69.05 (68.17)	5.07 5.08	8.22 8.37	8.25 8.81	4.50
[Ni(HDPB) ₂ 2H ₂ O] (Greenish yellow, 226)	69.08 (68.19)	5.34 5.08	8.03 8.37	8.30 8.78	3.08
[Cu(HDPB) ₂] (Buff, 250)	71.70 (71.52)	4.48 4.70	8.63 8.78	10.03 9.97	2.00
[Zn(HDPB) ₂] (White, 255)	71.81 (71.32)	4.64 4.69	8.27 8.76	10.17 10.22	Dia
[MoO ₂ (HDPB) ₂] (Yellow, 220)	65.60 (64.96)	4.12 4.27	8.07 7.98	14.00 13.67	Dia
[UO ₂ (HDPB) ₂]2H ₂ O (Chocolate, 228)	52.49 (51.82)	3.76 3.86	6.77 6.36	26.95 27.05	Dia

bond has been described to absorb at a considerably higher region around 970–980 cm^{-1} ¹². In the present case a weak band at 820 cm^{-1} in UO_2^{II} -HDPB complex corresponds to symmetric UO_2 stretching vibration and a broad band at 905 cm^{-1} to asymmetric UO_2 stretching.

Magnetic properties : From magnetic moment data (Table 1) the number of unpaired electrons were found out.

The results gave two different behaviours : (i) complexes Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were found to contain 5, 4, 5, 3, 2 and 1 unpaired electrons respectively, showing paramagnetic behaviour, (ii) complexes of Ti^{IV} , V^{V} , Cr^{VI} , Zn^{II} , Mo^{VI} and U^{VI} were found to contain no unpaired electrons showing diamagnetic behaviour. The results showed that the charge of the metal ion in free (uncomplexed) state is retained in the complexes after complexation. This was specially true for multivalent elements such as Ti, Cr, V, Mo and U which are very susceptible to oxidation-reduction. On the basis of literature data^{13,14} all the complexes except Zn^{II} and Cu^{II}

could be assigned octahedral geometry; Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes being tetrahedral and square-planar respectively.

Reflectance spectra : The results of diffused reflectance spectra of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of HDPB are reported in Table 2 alongwith the absorption bands and tentative assignments. On the basis of literature data¹⁵ the complexes of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} are found to be octahedral. The Cu^{II} complex is found to be square-planar. Electronic spectra of the complexes of Ti^{IV} , V^{V} , Cr^{VI} (all $3d^{10}$), Mo^{VI} ($4d^0$), U^{VI} ($5f^0$) and Zn^{II} ($3d^0$) could not furnish any useful information about geometry of the complexes as there is no unpaired electron present in the orbitals and hence $d-d$ transitions which are generally responsible for visible spectra are not possible. Solid reflectance spectra and solution spectra in chloroform showed some absorbance peaks in the uv and near-visible region which might be due to charge transfer from $\text{M} \rightarrow \text{L}$ or $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{M}$. For V^{V} -HDPB complex, distinct bands in the visible region (400–700 nm) were observed which may be due to charge transfer.

The peaks in the low energy visible region in these complexes may be due to metal $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. On the basis of magnetic properties and literature data these complexes are found to be high-spin octahedral (sp^3d^2) except that of Zn^{II} for which tetrahedral (sp^3) geometry is assigned.

TABLE 2—REFLECTANCE DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd	λ_{max}		Assignment
	nm	KK	
[Mn(HDPB) ₂ ·2H ₂ O]	395	25.32	${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(D)$
	555	18.02	${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$
[Fe ^{II} (HDPB) ₂ ·2H ₂ O]	600	16.66	C.T.
	870	11.49	${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$
[Fe ^{III} (HDPB) ₃ ·2H ₂ O]	550	18.18	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$
	820	12.19	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$
[Co(HDPB) ₂ ·2H ₂ O]	470	21.28	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$
	540	18.52	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$
[Ni(HDPB) ₂ ·2H ₂ O]	390	25.64	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
	710	14.08	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$
[Cu(HDPB) ₂]	440	22.73	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$
	820	12.19	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$

Thermal analysis : It is observed that water of hydration has been eliminated at 150–200° which suggests the presence of water of hydration as coordination water as well as crystal one. Water eliminating below 150° can be considered as free crystal water and eliminating above 150° may be due to its coordination to the metal ion¹⁶. Beyond 200° there is a gradual loss in weight showing decomposition of the complex and removal of first ligand molecule. The complexes of Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Mo^{VI} are found to contain no hydrated water. The complexes of other metals contain one or more water molecules in the form of either coordinated or crystal water.

In the present studies initial decomposition temperature have been used to determine thermal stability of metal complexes¹⁶. The relative thermal stability for HDPB complexes decreases in the order : $Zn^{II} > Cu^{II} > Ti^{IV} = Cr^{VI} > Co^{II} > Mn^{II} > U^{VI}$
 $Ni^{II} > Fe^{II} > V^V = Mo^{VI} > Fe^{III}$.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. The solvents were purified and dried whenever necessary.

N-Hydroxy-N,N'-diphenylbenzamidine (HDPB) :

The ligand *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine was synthesised by known method¹⁷. *N*-Phenylhydroxylamine was prepared by controlled reduction of distilled nitrobenzene¹⁸. *N*-Phenylbenzimidoyl chloride was prepared by the action of thionyl chloride on benzanilide. Benzamidoyl chloride was distilled under reduced pressure (175/12 mm) and dissolved in diethyl ether. The condensation of *N*-phenylbenzamidoyl chloride and *N*-phenylhydroxylamine led to *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine hydrochloride, which on treatment with dilute ammonia (trituration) yielded *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (HDPB).

Metal complexes : Metal salts of Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} were taken as the respective acetates. Fe^{II} was taken in the form of ferrous ammonium sulphate, Ti^{IV} as titanium sulphate, V^V as ammonium metavanadate, Cr^{VI} as potassium chromate, Mo^{VI} as ammonium molybdate and U^{VI} as uranyl nitrate. Solutions of the metal salts were prepared in distilled water and the ligand solution in ethanol. Ethanolic solution of ligand (10%) and aqueous solution of metal salt were mixed in 2 : 1 (L : M) ratio for Ti^{IV} , V^V , Cr^{VI} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mo^{VI} and U^{VI} complexes and in 3 : 1 (L : M) ratio for Fe^{III} complex. The mixture was digested on boiling water-bath for ~ 0.5 h with occasional stirring. The complexes formed were filtered and washed with water and suitable absolute alcohol-water mixture (viz. cold water and 5% alcohol for U^{VI} , Cr^{VI} , cold water and 15% alcohol for V^V , Ti^{IV} ; hot water and 10% alcohol for Fe^{III} and hot water and 25% alcohol for Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mo^{VI}). The separated complexes were dried in an oven at moderate temperatures (20–60°).

Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy's method at room temperature. Electronic and reflectance spectra were recorded on a Varian DMS80 spectrophotometer and ir spectra were taken in KBr. Thermogravimetric experiment was performed on a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 analyser with a TADS computer system with heating rate 10° min. Conductivity was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity meter in nitrobenzene. Elemental analyses were obtained by using a THOMAS C, N analyser and a Coleman N analyser.

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